

Navigating the Complexity: Acute on Chronic Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID)Eve Thomas¹, Sujani BK², Urvashi³, Gayatri Devi⁴¹Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, M.S Ramaiah Medical College Hospital and Research Centre²Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, M.S Ramaiah Medical College Hospital and Research Centre³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, M.S Ramaiah Medical College Hospital and Research Centre⁴Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, M.S Ramaiah Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

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Abstract:

Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is a syndrome that predominately affects cisgender women of reproductive age and can lead to chronic pelvic pain and infertility. Endometritis, salpingitis, tubo-ovarian abscess, and pelvic peritonitis are all on the spectrum of inflammatory processes comprising PID. The basic aim of the study is to effectively manage and treat acute on chronic pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) to prevent early complications. A 32-year-old woman, gravida 2 para 2 (P2L2), with a history of two previous lower segment cesarean sections (LSCS), presented with complaints of abdominal pain and heavy menstrual bleeding for the past 5 years. These symptoms worsened significantly over the last 2 days, accompanied by fever, vomiting and generalised weakness. PID is mostly diagnosed clinically. Imaging has a limited role. Surgical management is the treatment of choice with repeated exacerbations of PID. The extensive pelvic pathology identified on imaging, coupled with her systemic signs of sepsis, indicates the need for aggressive and comprehensive treatment. This case highlights the importance of timely diagnosis and management of PID to prevent complications such as infertility, chronic pelvic pain, and systemic infections.

Keywords: Pelvic Inflammatory Disease, Chronic Pelvic Pain, Sepsis.

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Introduction

Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is a syndrome that predominately affects cisgender women of reproductive age and can lead to chronic pelvic pain and infertility. Endometritis, salpingitis, tubo-ovarian abscess, and pelvic peritonitis are all on the spectrum of inflammatory processes comprising PID. Because PID can be symptomatic or asymptomatic, it is often left undiagnosed and untreated [1]. Even when symptoms occur, the diagnosis of PID based on clinical signs and symptoms is often inaccurate. Many women given a diagnosis of PID have no evidence of genital tract infection, while other women learn that they have had PID only when they learn that they have tubal factor infertility. Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) represents a significant health challenge, affecting millions of women worldwide and often leading to severe complications if left untreated [2]. The condition is characterized by the inflammation of the female reproductive organs, primarily caused by sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and other bacterial

infections. Among the various presentations of PID, the acute on chronic form poses unique challenges for diagnosis and management [3]. This dual condition not only complicates clinical assessment but also increases the risk of long-term sequelae, including chronic pain and infertility [3]. Understanding the interplay between acute exacerbations and chronic PID is crucial for healthcare providers to develop effective treatment strategies and improve patient outcomes. In this exploration, we will delve into the pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and management strategies of acute on chronic PID, highlighting the importance of a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of this complex condition [4]. The pathophysiology of PID involves the ascent of pathogens from the lower genital tract to the upper reproductive organs, including the uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries. Acute PID typically results from an acute infection that causes inflammation and damage to these structures. In contrast, chronic PID

arises from repeated infections or unresolved acute episodes, leading to persistent inflammation and scarring [5]. The acute on chronic presentation occurs when a new acute infection exacerbates an already established chronic condition. This can result in more severe symptoms, increased tissue damage, and heightened risks of complications, such as abscess formation or ectopic pregnancy [6]. The clinical manifestations of acute on chronic PID can be diverse and may vary significantly among individuals. Common symptoms include pelvic pain, fever, abnormal vaginal discharge, and dyspareunia (pain during intercourse) [7]. However, in cases where chronic PID is present, the symptoms may be subtler and can easily be overlooked. Women may experience chronic pelvic pain that flares up during acute episodes, leading to misdiagnosis or delayed treatment [8].

Furthermore, some patients may remain asymptomatic, emphasizing the importance of regular gynecological examinations and screenings for STIs to facilitate early detection and intervention. Diagnosing acute on chronic PID requires a thorough clinical evaluation, including a detailed patient history and physical examination [9].

Healthcare providers often utilize pelvic examinations to assess tenderness, adnexal masses, and other signs of inflammation. Laboratory tests, such as nucleic acid amplification tests (NAATs) for STIs, can help identify underlying infections [10]. Additionally, imaging studies, such as transvaginal ultrasound or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), may be employed to visualize pelvic organs and identify complications such as abscesses or hydrosalpinx [11].

The basic aim of the study is to effectively manage and treat acute on chronic pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) to prevent early complications.

Case Description

A 32-year-old woman, gravida 2 para 2 (P2L2), with a history of two previous lower segment cesarean sections (LSCS), presented with complaints of abdominal pain and heavy menstrual bleeding for the past 5 years and these symptoms worsened significantly over the last 2 days, accompanied by fever and vomiting and generalised weakness.

History:

- Complaints of chronic pain abdomen and heavy menstrual bleeding for past 5 years
- Aggravated pain abdomen and generalized weakness for the past 2 days
- Fever and vomiting present for the past 2 days.
- Chronic anaemia with multiple blood transfusions

On Admission:

- **Pallor:** present
- **Pulse rate:** 80 beats per minute, regular, low volume
- **Blood pressure:** 70/50 mmHg, patient shifted to ICU managed with noradrenaline to stabilize the hypotension.
- **Peripheral smear:** microcytic hypochromic anaemia with neutrophilia
- **Urine culture:** No growth of organisms
- **Blood cultures:** Growth of *Pseudomonas* species, started on intravenous antibiotics.

Examination:

- Tenderness in the left iliac fossa and left forniceal tenderness were noted on abdominal and pelvic examination, raising suspicion of a pelvic inflammatory process.

Investigations:

Abdominal and pelvis Ultrasound Report (06.06.2024): An abdominal ultrasound revealed that the liver, gall bladder, pancreas, spleen, and kidneys appeared normal in size and echo texture, with no focal lesions. However, a 4 × 4 mm polyp was noted in the gall bladder. The uterus was noted to be slightly enlarged, measuring 72 × 48 × 24 mm, with an endometrial thickness of 4.2 mm. The left ovary was bulky, measuring 40 × 34 mm, with multiple follicles observed, while the right ovary appeared normal. A dilated, tubular anechoic structure was seen in the left adnexa, likely representing left hydrosalpinx, with internal echoes suggesting infection. No free fluid was observed in the abdomen or pelvis. The impression was consistent with a gall bladder polyp, likely infective left hydrosalpinx, and free-floating internal echoes in the urinary bladder, indicating infection.

MRI Abdomen & Pelvis Report (07.06.2024): The MRI of the abdomen and pelvis showed mild bilateral pleural effusion, indicating fluid accumulation in the chest cavity. The uterus was found to be retroflexed and retroverted, measuring 40 × 41 × 97 mm, with a post-LSCS scar noted on its anterior aspect. The endometrium was measured at 10 mm in thickness. The right ovary appeared normal in size, measuring 19 × 30 mm, while the left ovary was enlarged at 30 × 25 mm with a dominant follicle measuring 29 × 21 mm. The left fallopian tube was dilated and convoluted, measuring 29 mm, with evidence of fluid-filled levels indicating salpingitis. Mild free fluid was also detected in the abdomen and the pouch of Douglas. The impression from the MRI was suggestive of left-sided salpingitis with hematosalpinx, mild ascites, and bilateral pleural effusion.

Figure 1: This axial MRI scan shows a cross-section of the pelvic region

There is evidence of multiple tubular structures and possible cystic formations in the pelvic cavity, with hyperintense (bright) areas suggesting fluid accumulation or inflammation.

The patient underwent a total abdominal hysterectomy with left salpingo oophorectomy with right salpingectomy.

Intra operative findings

- Dense adhesions noted, uterus densely adhered to the anterior abdominal wall.
- Left Tubo-ovarian abscess noted and left salpingo oophorectomy done.
- Right fallopian tube appeared edematous. Right salpingectomy done.
- Adhesions released and total abdominal hysterectomy done and specimen sent for histopathological examination.

Figure 2: Histopathology confirmed the diagnosis of acute on chronic PID

Discussion

Acute on chronic PID occurs when there is an acute flare-up of infection superimposed on a pre-existing chronic inflammatory condition. In this case, the chronic component of her disease may have been related to longstanding inflammation and infection within the pelvic organs, possibly due to recurrent infections or subclinical episodes of PID [12]. This probably true as the woman developed fever, vomiting and severe abdominal pain within

the few days prior to the surgery which most probably portend an acute exacerbation of the disease due to ongoing infection with fallopian tubes, ovaries as well as suppurative peritonitis of the lower abdomen [13].

This is in harmony with the imaging reports, which revealed salpingitic processes, hydrosalpinx and associated free fluid collections in the POD region of the pelvis [14]. However, *Pseudomonas* can be a nosocomial infection or an opportunistic pathogen,

particularly in the immunocompromised or those with an underlying chronic disease, including anemia such as this patient. The patient's hypotension and septic condition at admission demonstrated the systemic involvement in the infection, the emergence of *Pseudomonas* indicates a more virulent or atypical process that needs specific antibiotics [15]. So MRI and ultrasound findings can give essential information about the degree of pelvic pathology. In the MRI scan, retroflexion and retroversion of the uterus with a post-LSCS scar was documented and the bilateral pleural effusion also pointed towards peritoneal/thoracic spread [16].

Evaluation of the left adnexa revealed prominent pathologies; a markedly dilated fallopian tube with tubular formation having fluid filled segments, indicating salpingitis and hydrosalpinx. This is suggestive of tubal inflammation and infection which if not treated would result into fallopian tube damage.

The examination report elaborated the ultrasound findings also revealing a significantly enlarged left adnex with internal echoes suspicious of infection or abscess formation, and enlarged left ovary. Further, Internal echoes floating freely were seen in the bladder cavity which may be associated with secondary infection of the urinary tract caused by the inflammation of the pelvic organs [17].

The care for this patient likewise involves the treatment of its short term and long term manifestations. Intravenous broad-spectrum antibiotics are mandatory to manage the acute phase of the infection, and antibiotics against *Pseudomonas*, depending on culture and sensitivity data [18]. Due to the septic status, hypotension and presence of condition, that requires strict monitoring of her hemodynamic status support with fluid therapy and use of vasopressors such as noradrenaline.

The patient's abscesses may require drains, or additional procedures if medical management of the infection does not suffice [19]. If this line of treatment does not work, then removal of pus by aspiration or operation to remove badly damaged fallopian tubes (salpingectomy) may be necessary. Long term measures, therefore, should aim at avoiding a repeat episode of PID as well as addressing any fertility issues because of the high likelihood of tubal pathology [20].

Conclusion

PID is mostly diagnosed clinically. Imaging has a limited role. Surgical management is the treatment of choice with repeated exacerbations of PID. The extensive pelvic pathology identified on imaging, coupled with her systemic signs of sepsis, indicates the need for aggressive and comprehensive treatment. This case highlights the importance of timely diagnosis and management of PID to

prevent complications such as infertility, chronic pelvic pain, and systemic infections. Long-term follow-up will be essential to ensure full recovery and to address any residual complications from the chronic inflammation and infection.

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